
ATLAS Milestone 2

Scope of sectoral activities and ocean services

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Author:	Anthony Grehan, National University of Ireland Galway

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This milestone is the first step towards the preparation of **D6.1: Sectoral activities, institutional landscape, existing management plans and MSP goals for each study** area due in month 12. A breakout session with all case study leaders was held during the kick-off meeting in Edinburgh on the 14th of June, 2016.

The session began with a discussion on how Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) could support Blue Growth. The following considerations were identified as important for industry:

- A social license to operate – compliant with legislation
- Faster passage through the maze of development regulations
- Virtual assessment of costs of any proposed new development
- Reduction in development costs if development to go ahead linked to:
 - Reduced costs of actual Environmental Impact Assessment
 - Reduced transaction costs, administration, legal costs etc., through shared actions, i.e. not starting from scratch
 - Addressing sensitivity/resilience of species/habitats to stressors
- Creation of more certainty for investment decisions
- Creation of opportunities for multi-sectoral use of space/infrastructure.

In addition, the participants discussed Information flow between WPs and made the following points:

- Exchange products will be mostly GIS layers
- WP5 will produce spatial valuations of ecosystem goods and services
 - WP5 will need delineated substrate and habitat maps showing the extent of mud, sand and VMEs in each case study
- WP7 Risk Assessment
 - Need to agree our risk assessment approach (relevant to WP 5, 6 and 7) – at meeting in Oxford (early September)
 - WP5 needs to input on risk to ecosystems goods and services
 - WP6 needs to input on risk to Good Environmental Status
- WP4 – seascape genetics map
 - Possible pilot: Spain to Ireland showing predicted habitat distributions for selected species overlain with seascape genetics.

The rest of the session was devoted to collective brainstorming to produce a matrix identifying potential Blue Growth opportunities in each Case Study (Table 1). This matrix will be used to ensure that all Blue Growth opportunities are included in the development of marine plans in at least one case study. The matrix will also inform WP5 deliberations.

	Lofoten-Vesteralen Observatory	North and West of Shetland	Rockall	Mingulay Reef Complex	Porcupine Seabight	Bay of Biscay	Gulf of Cadiz/Alboran Sea - Medwaves	Azores	Deep-Links - Gulf of Cadiz	Davis Strait	Flemish Cap	Canyon Province, US Atlantic Bight
Jurisdiction	EEZ	EEZ	EEZ/ABNJ/Ext CS	EEZ	EEZ	EEZ	EEZ	EEZ	EEZ	EEZ	ABNJ/Ext CS	EEZ/ABNJ
Conservation management	X	X	X	X (SAC)		X		X		X	X	X
Reason for Spatial Management Plan?	Existing - fishing and tourism (no oil - at the moment), offshore windmills, Zooplankton - Calanus	Cables, fishing, oil and gas, tourism	Fisheries	Fisheries (demersal and pelagic), cables, tourism,	Multiple stakeholders; conservation importance; Oil and gas exploitation	Military, fisheries, biotechnology, shipping, fishing for litter	Fisheries, recreational fisheries, shipping, cables (?), aquaculture, tourism	Fishing (bottom and pelagic) longlining, shipping, cables, tourism, scientific research		Fisheries, oil and gas, tourism, indigenous fisheries	Fisheries, oil and gas, shipping, cables	Fisheries, recreational fisheries (?), cables, tourism, shipping, research
Blue Growth Scenarios												
Blue Economy												
<i>Minerals</i>	x						x	x				x
<i>Renewable energy</i>	x		?	?			x	x				
<i>Aquaculture</i>	x			x			x	x				
<i>Tourism</i>	x			x	?		x	x		x		x
<i>Eco-tourism</i>							x			x		x
<i>Biotechnology</i>	x	x	x	x	x		x	x		x	x	x
<i>Oil and gas</i>	x	x	x		x	?	x			x	x	x
<i>Carbon sequestration</i>	?											
<i>Shipping</i>	x	x	x	x		x	x	x		x	x	x
<i>Zooplankton</i>			x							x		
<i>Cables</i>		x		x	x	x	x	x			x	x
<i>New fisheries resources</i>		?	x	x	x	x		x		x	x	x
<i>Scientific (research) reference sites/observatories</i>		x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x
<i>Indigenous peoples</i>										x		
<i>Maritime security and surveillance</i>							x					x

Table 1: A matrix identifying potential Blue Growth opportunities in each case study area